

SURVEILLANCE CARD_WNF_Sentinel surveillance in chickens

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Sentinel surveillance in chickens.
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of possible virus circulation.
3	Target species and group	Chickens (<i>Gallus gallus</i>).
4	Target sector / production type	Backyard or purposefully placed sentinels.
5	Geographical area covered	Country-wide areas with suitable habitat for vectors: to be preferred areas where adult female mosquitoes lay eggs on the surface of fresh or stagnant water. Areas on the outskirts of cities and population centres, bordering forests and wetlands. (1)
6	Age group	No particular age targetting – all adults.
7	Sampling point and strategy	Different sampling strategies have been reported: random sampling of backyard hens in risk regions (2); or purposefully placing caged chickens as a sentinel monitoring strategy in areas with high risk for humans (3).
8	Sampling time period	Year-round / not limited; minimum annual time frame with the greatest diffusion of vectors: from March to November. (4)
9	Sampling matrix	Whole blood.
10	Type of disease indicators	Antibody detection, identification and isolation of the agent.
11	Sampling unit	Individual animal.
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	Sentinel surveillance can be achieved through regular monitoring of a random (or convenience) sample of the population, or through specific (targetted) sampling of animals meant to serve as early indicators to other species. The goal is not to have a representative sample, nor estimate any probabilistic incidence measure of disease burden. The sampling strategy should be aimed at early detection of cases.

13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Serological tests Antibodies can be identified in serum by IgM capture enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (IgM capture ELISA), haemagglutination inhibition (HI), IgG ELISA, plaque reduction neutralisation (PRN), and microtitre virus neutralisation (VN). (5)
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	This component aims at early detection of possible virus introduction.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	Not applicable.
18	References	<p>1) ECDC Culex pipiens - Factsheet for experts, last updated 15 Jun 2020</p> <p>2) Harun et al. 2021. Sentinel serosurveillance of backyard hens proved West Nile virus circulation in the western provinces of Turkey. Veterinary Medicine and Science, 7 (6), pp. 2348 – 2352. DOI: 10.1002/vms3.589</p> <p>3) Chaskopoulou A, Dovas CI, Chaintoutis SC, Kashefi J, Koehler P, Papanastassopoulou M. Detection and early warning of West Nile Virus circulation in Central Macedonia, Greece, using sentinel chickens and mosquitoes. Vector Borne Zoonotic Dis. 2013 Oct;13(10):723-32. doi: 10.1089/vbz.2012.1176. Epub 2013 Aug 6. PMID: 23919609.</p> <p>4) TECHNICAL REPORT Field sampling methods for mosquitoes, sandflies, biting midges and ticks VectorNet project 2014–2018</p>

		5) WOAH Terrestrial Manual Chapter 3.1.25. about West Nile fever (version adopted in May 2018)
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